

EFFECT OF COTTON STORAGE METHODS ON FIBER QUALITY

Egamberdiyev Fazliddin Otakulovich

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute.

Department of natural fibers and fabric processing PhD, associate professor

Kadirov Shakhobiddin

Jizzakh Polytechnic Institute

Assistant of the Department of Natural Fibers and Fabric Processing

Annotation: This article analyzes the effect of cotton storage methods on fiber quality. In addition, the importance of the opinions of scientists in cotton farming is also mentioned in the article.

Key words: fiber, cotton, oil protein, equipment, cotton cleaning industry, temperature, cleaning work.

Increasing the efficiency of cotton production in agriculture, increasing the quantity and quality of products obtained from cotton depends on the quality of cotton seeds and the quality of the prepared seeds. "Uzpakhtasanoat" association attaches great importance to the creation of new technologies and equipment and their implementation in cotton ginning plants in order to improve the quality of cotton storage. Based on the above, we conducted scientific research in order to study the improvement of the methods of storage of picked cotton. Cotton varieties grown in Uzbekistan are quick-ripening, fertile, high fiber yield, good fiber quality, rich in oil and protein, resistant to adverse environmental conditions (soil salinity, low temperature, heat, drought and etc.) are also required to be resistant to diseases and pests, adapted to the mechanization of inter-row work, machine harvesting, and have other valuable economic signs and characteristics.

The quality of the seeds planted next year in cotton farming depends on the timing of their picking and the extent to which the harvesting season is organized, storage processes and preparation for planting are carried out in accordance with the state standard requirements. A lot of scientists have made a great contribution with their experiences and innovations to further improve the quality of cotton in cotton factories. As a result, today almost all cotton ginning factories in our country have been transferred to the cluster system and are again provided with modern equipment and facilities.

This year, it is planned to plant seeds of 15 fast-growing, 5 medium-growing, and 8 promising varieties of cotton in the regions of our country. This, in

turn, means that 55.0% of the total area planned to be sown with seeds was planted with fast-growing varieties, 30.0% with medium-growing varieties, 6.5% with promising varieties and 8.5% with new varieties. Varieties should be adaptable to environmental changes, including soil moisture deficiency, salt-resistant, and contribute to the improvement of agro-background.

The C-6524 cotton variety, distinguished by the quality of its fiber and high yield, is more adaptable to environmental changes compared to other varieties. and 20-50 percent of areas in Syrdarya regions are planned to be planted. Growers of Andijan, Namangan and Fergana regions planted 60-70 percent of the cotton area with high-yielding varieties such as "Andijan-35", "Andijan-36", "Andijan-37", "Namangan-77", C-8290. planned.

Taking into account the growing demand for type IV fiber C-6524 in the cotton market, it is possible to plant this variety in 15-35 percent of the cotton-growing areas of Jizzakh, Namangan, Syrdaryo, Tashkent, and Fergana regions this year. It's going on. In addition, the salt-resistant, quick-growing "AnBoyovut-2" variety is planted on 20-30 percent of the cotton fields in Jizzakh, Sirdarya, and Navoi regions, which allows for abundant harvest even in the soil and climate conditions of this region. Cotton selection, industrial varieties and classes are stored in a special order in special open areas in tarpaulin covered warehouses and covered warehouses.

Open areas for storing seed cotton are 40 cm from the ground. high, their surface is 25x14 m. or 22x11 m. will be. 150-400 t to such open areas. seed cotton can be stored up to Djaborov G. D., Baltaboyev S.D. according to the results of the research carried out, with the change in the yield of processed seed cotton, the fiber residue of the seed also changes. For this purpose, the de-fibered seeds flow over a vibrating net. The cleaned seed falls out of the mesh hole as required. Seeds with a fiber residue of 0.12-0.19% and a moisture content of 12% are left on the net for re-cleaning. It can be seen that poorly dried seeds have a negative effect on the sorting process.

Khodzhiyev M.T., Tadzhiyev U.S., Mubarakov A.Y. According to (1999), cotton received from farms is stored in various ways in cotton processing plants and points. Cotton absorbs a certain amount of moisture during winter storage in bundles, warehouses, and storage under covered sheds under various humidity conditions. In this case, a wet environment can have a negative effect on cotton fiber and seed (especially seed seed). An increase in humidity and an extreme drop or rise in temperature causes the deterioration of the quality of the seed, its germination, and the deterioration of the quality of the fiber. In particular, it is necessary to store seed

seeds in closed warehouses, but second and third generation seed cottons and seeds are also stored in barns.

Mannopov A., Boronov H. (2001) stated that the cotton ginning industry is the last stage in the Republican cotton complex. Therefore, the improvement of the quality of the work of the industry will mainly depend on the organization of its work and the equipping of it with modern tools and equipment. The effect of temperature on the moisture content of cotton during storage is important in one way or another for the quality of seed and fiber. If the temperature in the chamber increases, self-heating occurs, as a result, the respiration of the seed accelerates, which leads to the premature consumption of the available energy reserves in the seed.

With the increase of machine harvesting in the seeded cotton crop, the moisture and dirtiness of the cotton increases. Such a state of cotton leads to increased drying and cleaning operations in ginning plants.

In cotton ginning plants, seed products separated from fiber are collected in tanks and stored for 1-4 months. During the storage period, the temperature is mainly kept the same. The seed is depilated first by fire and then by 96% sulfuric acid. Up to 30% of seeds that do not meet the requirements of GOST are sent to oil extraction enterprises.

Cotton fiber, lint and fiber waste bales are stacked on top of each other in sheds, if there are no special sheds, they are stacked with logs under the bales and covered with a tarpaulin. According to the results of the experiment, it was found that the quality of cotton fiber stored in a closed state is 2.3-3.1 percent higher than that stored in an open state.

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